

DATASETLY: A Knowledge Base of Curated Citations of Large Datasets for Science and Research *

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Abstract: Datasetly platform is intended to simplify the process of finding and referencing reliable high quality datasets and data studies for science and research. It is a collated online knowledge base of curated resolvable citations of data sets and data studies that are distributed across several repositories and platforms worldwide. **DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15883438.**

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I. INTRODUCTION

Datasetly platform at the time of this writing does not host or provide datasets [53]. It is an informational knowledge base of curated citations and DOI links of large datasets that are already hosted and spread across several different repositories and platforms worldwide. It hosts DOI links and citations of datasets with the goal of illustrating how such a knowledge base would support science and research through discovery and attributions of reliable datasets. In that respect, it also embraces the importance of having persistent digital object identifiers (DOIs) for hosted datasets. DOI links are resolvable and provide persistent and reliable means for discovery of datasets and related data studies and knowledge.

II. JUSTIFICATION

Large-scale open access datasets are spread across many different institutional and scientific research data repositories, and numerous other open access data ventures and dataset hosting initiatives. Examples include Zenodo, Kaggle, data.gov, World Bank Open Data (data.worldbank.org), data.org, Our World in Data (ourworldindata.org), OECD Data, OpenML, IMF Data, WHO Data, WRI Data (wri.org/data), Data Commons (datacommons.org), Nature Scientific Data (nature.com/sdata), Open Data Handbook (opendatahandbook.org), The Humanitarian Data Exchange (data.humdata.org), NASA Earthdata (earthdata.nasa.gov), Climate Data Online (ncei.noaa.gov/cdo-web), European data (data.europa.eu/en), Data USA (datausa.io), GitHub, data.un.org, Google dataset search, PANGAEA, [41], MDPI data (mdpi.com/journal/data), Earth System Science

Data (essd.copernicus.org), Figshare, Global Fire Emissions Database (globalfiredata.org), ESS archive (essopenarchive.org), Harvard Dataverse (dataverse.harvard.edu), Madrigal Database (cedar.openmadrigal.org), and many others.

Although several entities and institutions provide datasets that are openly accessible, historically, the hosting sites and/or URLs are not guaranteed to be permanent and persistent. There have been many instances where the URLs of hosted datasets have been changed, moved, or completely ceased to exist. This is especially critical for hosted datasets that are relied upon by scientists and researchers for long-term studies and research. Thus, it is important that hosted datasets are assigned some kind of long-term, persistent, "resolvable" and citable identifiers such as through the DOI link services.

Harvard Dataverse and **Zenodo** are great examples of how datasets that are assigned DOIs can help solve such problems, as they allow for data versioning through DOI links. **PANGAEA** "uses an organized approach to long-term preservation, with continued access for data types despite format changes", and "ensures continuity of all archived data and takes responsibility in the case of a temporary or permanent break in service" [41]. And **Figshare** hosts open access citable datasets with version control, citation counts, and a host of other useful features for research and scientific applications. Several other examples can be given of similar different platforms offering dataset hosting.

By embracing the opportunities brought about by the open data initiatives using DOI-centric hosting solutions of datasets, Datasetly is an example of how a knowledge base of carefully curated citations can aid and simplify the discovery of reliable high quality datasets for science and research.

III. THEMATIC EXAMPLES

Figure I shows a simple interface of the platform for searching and exploring dataset information. Thematic large datasets and studies exploring big ideas with data are considered, for which carefully curated citations and references are compiled. Thematic categories of the curated information are thus defined, examples of which are alphabetically:

- astronomy and space science [15, 16, 25, 26, 29, 83, 84, 85];
- business, finance, economics [6, 48, 50, 51, 71, 79, 80, 81];

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- climate, weather, drought, water resources [2, 4, 7, 17, 19, 21, 30, 33, 39, 40, 42, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47, 52, 54, 55, 57, 58, 59, 60, 61, 62, 63, 64, 65, 66, 67, 68, 69, 74, 75, 82, 88, 92, 93, 98, 99];
- earth resources, minerals, discovery, mining [24, 50, 77, 78];
- environment [4, 7, 17, 19, 42, 43, 44, 45, 47, 49, 50, 52, 55, 63, 64, 65, 66, 67, 68, 71, 72, 73, 77, 78, 82, 90, 98, 100, 101, 102, 103, 104];
- exploring big ideas with data [8, 17, 19, 20, 21, 22, 25, 31, 32, 38, 44, 46, 47, 48, 49, 54, 55, 56, 57, 58, 59, 60, 61, 62, 65, 66, 67, 71, 93, 94, 95, 97, 98, 99, 100, 101, 102, 105];
- geohazards [4, 17, 30, 37, 73, 82, 88, 90, 91, 96, 100, 101, 102];
- geospatial [1, 3, 4, 7, 8, 19, 21, 23, 32, 36, 38, 47, 48, 49, 50, 70, 71, 72, 76, 82, 86, 87, 88, 90, 91, 94, 95, 96, 97, 98, 100, 101, 102];
- government, policy, politics [3, 5, 6, 45, 48, 51, 63, 64, 77, 78];
- healthcare [3, 28, 87, 89, 97, 106, 107, 108, 109, 110, 111];
- infrastructure [4, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 16, 57, 63, 64, 71, 72, 87, 94, 95, 98, 100, 101, 102, 103, 104];
- land, agriculture, food security [7, 17, 34, 42, 43, 44, 45, 49];
- large-scale datasets [2, 6, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 18, 19, 20, 21, 22, 23, 24, 27, 28, 31, 32, 34, 35, 36, 37, 43, 44, 45, 46, 47, 48, 49, 50, 52, 54, 57, 58, 59, 60, 61, 62, 63, 64, 65, 66, 67, 68, 69, 70, 71, 72, 73, 74, 75, 76, 83, 84, 86, 87, 88, 91, 92, 93, 95, 97, 98, 99, 100, 101, 102];
- public health [3, 5, 48, 63, 64, 67, 73, 106, 107, 108, 109, 110];
- satellites, earth observation and PNT solutions [1, 2, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 18, 20, 21, 22, 23, 27, 30, 31, 32, 33, 35, 36, 37, 44, 47, 49, 52, 67, 69, 70, 71, 72, 82, 88, 89, 91, 92, 93, 94, 95, 97, 98, 100, 101, 102, 105, 110];
- space exploration [25, 26, 83, 84, 85];
- telecommunications [32, 38, 55, 56, 89];
- urban informatics [8, 48, 55, 56, 63, 64, 71, 72, 94, 95, 98, 100, 101, 102, 103, 104].

The knowledge base information are also tagged with several various keywords so that a user looking for information by search can find relevant dataset information if the keyword matches any one or a combination of the tags. Examples of tags include such as AI, big data, dataset, earth observation, geospatial, global science, GNSS, gravity, healthcare, health science, ionosphere, machine learning, medical, planetary science, PNT, positioning, regional science, remote sensing, satellites, sensors, technology, timing, travel, weather, and so forth.

FIGURE I: DATASETLY WEB INTERFACE, JULY 2025

IV. IMPORTANT FEATURES AND USE CASES

Datasetly provides the means for data enthusiasts, scholars, researchers, authors, scientists, and institutions to support dataset attributions and citations. Through the platform, users can discover relevant information and also add new information to help support the database.

Data scientists and researchers often require high-quality datasets for research, model training, and analysis. This usually translates to considerable amount of time and effort spent on researching and finding suitable datasets.

As one of the feasible solutions, Datasetly platform offers a centralized knowledge base with curated DOI and citation links to datasets and related studies that are hosted across several different repositories and platforms worldwide. This allows for better experience in exploring datasets and finding the best fit for the needs. For example, if a data scientist were working on a project related to GNSS or healthcare data, they might use it to find relevant datasets and research papers.

Datasetly focuses on datasets across thematic domains, providing references and citations for thematic datasets, enabling researchers to find and properly attribute and acknowledge data sources in their work. It simplifies the process of finding relevant datasets for projects by providing curated references and resolvable links that are also thematically findable.

In summary, the benefits and features include the following:

- focuses on providing carefully curated and reliable references, potentially saving data scientists time and effort in searching for appropriate datasets;
- highlights datasets and studies that explore “big ideas” with data, covering areas like earth resources, healthcare, space exploration, and more;
- a centralized resource offering compiled DOI links, references and citations for large datasets and studies, making it easier for data scientists to find relevant resources;
- helps understand data context by providing the citations, links and references to relevant publications, and thus helps data users understand the context and background of the datasets they are using;
- the links and references lead to the original source of the dataset, allowing data scientists to download or access the data for their analysis;
- scientists and researchers can search the platform using keywords related to their research topic or the type of data they need, for example, “groundwater,” “climate change,” “healthcare”, ”gnss”, ”satellites”, etc.
- supports data science through discoverable, citable, persistent, and reliable linked information on datasets and scholarly, peer-reviewed data studies.

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